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Rehabilitation of Kileleshwa Roads, Kenya.

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Abstract

Nairobi has been rapidly urbanizing ever since the independence years. The increase in the urban population has brought about numerous challenges such as overcrowding, pollution, densification of existing developments, urban sprawl and congested infrastructure. These challenges have put enormous pressure on the government to create working systems that can accommodate the ever-growing urban developmental needs. Major efforts have been directed towards rehabilitation of existing buildings, roads and public spaces in order to mitigate these problems.

Kileleshwa is one of the areas experiencing intense densification as it transformed from a low-density high-income area, to a high-density middle-income area. This has made the existing infrastructural services to be heavily strained as they have not been expanded to match the increasing density standards. Also, the property values in Kileleshwa have skyrocketed putting intense pressure on the government and local authorities to enhance existing infrastructure standards so that investors can recoup their investments. Therefore, the main objective of this project is rehabilitation and upgradation of existing Kileleshwa roads, in order to accommodate additional traffic loading brought about by the expanded vertical and horizontal housing densification.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Organizational background and overview

Over the years, the major sign of growth of infrastructure in Kenya has been in the roads sector. From the Kenya Roads Act No.2 of 2007, Part II, various authorities were established to ensure proper management and comprehensive administration of Kenyan roads. Kenya Urban Roads Authority (KURA), under the act, has the perpetual responsibility for the management, development, rehabilitation and maintenance of all public roads in the cities and municipalities in Kenya except where those roads are national roads.

1.2. Functions of KURA

For the purposes of ensuring KURA discharges its responsibilities adequately, it has the following duties and powers:-

- a) Construction, upgradation, rehabilitation and maintenance of all roads under its control.
- b) Implementation of urban roads policies.
- c) Quality control of all roads works to standards defined by the Cabinet Secretary.
- d) Monitoring and proper evaluation of the use of urban roads.
- e) Liaison with other road authorities in the proper coordination and planning of operations.
- f) Control of urban road reserves and access to roadside developments.
- g) Ensuring adherence by motorists to the rules and regulations on axle load controls prescribed under regulations of the Traffic Act (Cap. 403).
- h) Overseeing management of traffic and road safety on urban roads.
- i) Collecting and collating all data related to the use of urban roads that maybe necessary in relation to future planning.
- j) Preparation of all road works programmes for all urban roads.

1.3. Organisation flowchart

1.4. Vision, mission and core values.

The mandate of KURA as defined in the Kenya Roads Act, 2007 is the management, development, rehabilitation and maintenance on national urban trunk roads. Its vision includes provision of world-class urban road networks for the purpose of sustainable development. KURA's mission is to provide and manage quality, safe and adequate urban road networks.

KURA's organisational core values are:

2. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

2.1. Introduction

The Rehabilitation of Kileleshwa Roads project was commissioned by KURA on October, 2021 under tender number, KURA/RMLF/HQ/270/2021-2022. Method of tendering was open and competitive. The standard specifications involved are; **Standard Specifications for Roads and Bridge Construction, Published by the Ministry of Transport and Communications of the Republic of Kenya, 1986 Edition**. Special specifications are supplementary to the Standard Specifications and in any case where there appears to be conflict between the two then the Special Specifications always take precedence.

2.2. Project location

The project roads are located in Kileleshwa area and have an approximate length of 6.8 km. The roads contained in this project are as follows;

Sample number.	Road Name	Length (km)
1	Mandera Road	1.00
2	Gichugu Road	0.60
3	Kandara Road	0.70
4	Ole Kejuado Road	0.40
5	Siaya Road	0.60
6	Tabere Crescent & Githunguri road	1.00
7	Statehouse Crescent	0.45
8	Kangundo Road	0.35
9	Makueni Road	0.40
10	Vihiga Road	0.60
11	Gatundu Road	0.70
Total		6.80

Table 1: Roads involved in the Rehabilitation of Kileleshwa roads project.

Figure 1: Geographical location of Kileleshwa roads

2.3 Project scope of works

The main objective of the project is Rehabilitation of infrastructure works in Kileleshwa roads.

The road works comprise the construction of approximately 6.8 Km of single carriageway, 6.0m wide, two-lane, bitumen standard roads within Kileleshwa area. Works to be executed under the Contract include the following:-

- Site clearance which includes removal of encroachments.
- Setting out and taking cross-sections.
- Removal of overburden.
- Removal of topsoil and expansive clays.
- Cut to spoil/fill for vertical alignment.
- Stock piling the existing gravel for reuse as fill material.
- Filling with gravel or approved materials for sub-grade and sub-base layers; and shoulders for rehabilitation sections.

- Hand packing for the base layer.
- Installation of kerbs for edge restraints on the carriageway.
- Regulation and surfacing with Asphalt Concrete on the carriageway.
- Construction of 1.5m to 2.0m walkway of concrete paving blocks surfacing.
- Overlay of all roads.
- Excavation of drains.
- Lining of drains using masonry/reinforced concrete.
- Installation of culverts and Invert Block Drains (IBDs) where applicable.
- Installation of shallow Invert Block Drains (IBDs) where applicable.
- Paving blocks surfacing for walkway and selected sections.
- Provision and erection of road furniture including road signs, road markings, edge marker posts, guardrails and other miscellaneous works.
- Provision of offices and laboratory for the Resident Engineer(s) and their staff.

3. ROAD CONSTRUCTION

Road construction basically is the process of installing appropriate soil stabilizers, asphalt, concrete and other materials on a well defined path/route to create a smooth paved surface for vehicles to traverse on. A road can also be defined as a mode of transportation which facilitates trips. A trip is a one-way person movement having two trip ends, an origin (the start of the trip) and a destination (the end of the trip).

Trips can be classified by:-

- a) Origin and destination.

Trips are divided into home-based and non-home-based trips. Home-based (HB) trips are those having one end of the trip at the home of the trip maker, while non-home-based (NHB) trips are those having neither end at the home of the trip maker.

Figure 2: Home-based and non-home based trips

- b) Trip purpose.

Trips can be classified based on the purpose of the journey as trips for work, education, recreation and other miscellaneous reasons. Work and education trips are usually called compulsory (or mandatory) trips and all the others are called discretionary or optional trips.

- c) Trip time of the day.

Trips are based on the time of the day when the trips are made. The proportion of journeys by different purposes usually varies greatly with the time of day, which is classified further into peak and off-peak trips. The early morning peak period is usually 7:00AM to 10:00AM and the evening peak period is usually 4:00PM-7:00PM. Every other hour is off peak.

d) Type of trip maker.

Individual travel behavior is heavily dependent on socio-economic attributes such as :-

- Car ownership (typically three strata: 0, 1 and 2 or more cars).
- Income level.
- Household size and structure (e.g.1,2,3,4).

3.1. Steps involved in road construction

As stated before, KURA's primary function is the management, development, rehabilitation and maintenance of national urban trunk roads like the ones in Kileleshwa. For these activities to be undertaken, we need to understand the step-by-step process on how roads are made and properly outline the steps involved in order to create a passable roadway. Normally, this task involves proper planning therefore; one must consider the project at hand in order to properly execute these functions.

When it comes to asphalt/concrete roads, the following steps are considered during construction;

Step 1: Planning

Step 2: Setting out

Step 3: Earthworks

Step 4: Paving

Step 5: Quality control

3.1.1. Planning

In any type of road construction, planning is the most initial step since by failing to prepare, you are most definitely preparing to fail. This involves assessing current and future traffic patterns, usually through the four-step travel model^[1], which is a ubiquitous framework for determining transportation forecasts that date back to the '50s. The four steps are described as follows:

1. Trip Generation

Trip generation refers to the estimation of the number of trips (by trip purpose) produced by or attracted to a Transport Analysis Zone (TAZ). This is the first phase of the transportation modelling which deals with surveys, data collection and inventory, therefore determining the frequency of origins and destinations of trips in each TAZ.

Factors governing trip generation and attraction rates.

- **Income-** Family income represents ability to pay for a journey. The higher the income, the higher the trip generation rate. The lower the income, the lower the trip generation rate.
- **Car ownership-** A car provides easy mobility, hence a car owning household will generate more trips than a non-car-owning household. Using the same logic, the more cars there are in a household, the more the number of trips generated.
- **Family size and composition-** The bigger the family, the more trips they are likely to generate. Besides the size, the composition of the family is itself important. For instance, if both wife and husband are employed, the number of trips will be more. If there are school-going children, the number of school-purpose trips will be large. Old persons especially retired ones are not expected to generate as many trips as younger ones.
- **Land use characteristics –** Different land uses produce different trip rates. For example, a residential area with a high density of dwellings produces more trips than one with a low density of dwellings.
- **Distance of the zone from the town centre-** The further the town centre, the fewer the trips are likely to be. Kileleshwa is relatively close to town therefore generates more trips.
- **Accessibility/efficiency of public transport system-** An easily accessible and efficient transport system generates more trips and reduces the number of private car trips
- **Employment opportunities, floor space in industrial and shopping units-** These govern the trip attraction rates

2. Trip Distribution

The purpose of trip distribution is to produce a trip table of the estimated number of trips from each TAZ to every other TAZ within the study area. Here, one ends up often using a gravity model calculation that takes into account the relative activity at the origin and destination as well as the travel cost to go between them. The Gravity Model assumes that the number of trips between two zones is;

- 1) Directly proportional to the trips produced and attracted to both zones, and
- 2) Inversely proportional to the travel time between the zones.

The Gravity Model formulation states that the number of trips between each zone is equal to:

$$T_{ij} = P_i * \frac{A_j F_{ij} K_{ij}}{\sum_{j=1}^n (A_j F_{ij} K_{ij})}$$

Where

T_{ij}	=	Number of trips from zone i to zone j
P_i	=	Number of trip productions in zone i
A_j	=	Number of trip attractions in zone j
F_{ij}	=	Friction factor (represents the spatial separation between zone i & zone j)
K_{ij}	=	Optional adjustment factor (fudge factor)-not recommended

Figure 3: Gravity model formulation

3. Mode Choice

Mode choice is the process whereby the means of travelling is determined. The means of travel is also referred to as the travel mode, which may be by private automobile, public transportation, walking, bicycling, or other means. Mode choice is an important part of the model and is used for analyses such as:

- Major transportation investment projects since they may attract travellers not only from competing facilities but also competing modes.
- Transit service changes, which may encourage or discourage travellers from using transit.
- Long-range forecasts, where changes in demographics or in travel conditions (e.g. increased congestion) may alter the relative worth of different modes for some or all travellers.

- Pricing policy analyses, which may discourage travellers from using modes with increased prices.
- Land use planning analyses, where changes in development patterns may make certain modes more or less attractive relative to others.

Factors that influence mode choice

- **Traveller characteristics (socio-demographics, attitudes, perceptions, lifestyle)**

The characteristics of individual travellers affect their choice of mode. These may include observed characteristics, such as age, gender, driver's license status, or worker or student status, and unobserved characteristics, such as awareness of transportation options, consideration of specific modes, attitudes, and personal preferences. Characteristics of a traveller's household, such as income level and vehicle availability, may also affect mode choice.

- **Modal availability and characteristics**

For a mode to be chosen, it must be available to the traveller. Availability of public transit modes is generally not restricted; however, there may be no reasonable transit paths for some origin-destination combinations. A transit mode is deemed to be available if the transit path building process is able to find a valid path from the origin to the destination.

- **Mode characteristics**

Mode characteristics are usually measures of the level of service provided by the mode. For non-motorized modes, characteristics are usually limited to time and or distance. Because speeds may vary much more among travellers for non-motorized than for motorized modes, it may be difficult to estimate travel times for individual travellers.

For bicycle modes, a limited amount of research has been done indicating that cyclists prefer paths that include dedicated bicycle facilities, fewer turns, less vehicular traffic, fewer traffic controls, smooth pavement, level terrain, and no on-street parking. Some of these characteristics, however, may be difficult to quantify in some modelling environments.

- **Characteristics of the journey**

Characteristics of the tour or trip may have an effect on the mode choice decision.

- **Time of day**

This may affect not only the level of transportation service but also considerations such as a higher preference for bicycling, walking, or waiting in daylight hours.

- **Land use**

Certain land use characteristics may favour the use of some modes. In general, more densely developed areas see higher shares of transit and walking modes. The land use characteristics that affect mode choice are often included in the form of variables representing density of development or other features near the origin or destination of the tour or trip. Some examples include:

- Population density.
- Employment density, often by type.
- Measures of “mixed land use” density that consider how much different types of development (e.g. commercial and residential) occur.
- Intersection density, which considers the density of the road network as well as its connectivity.

4. Network Assignment.

In the urban transportation planning and analysis, the network assignment specifically involves estimating travellers’ route choice behaviour when travel destinations and mode of travel are known. Origin-destination travel demand are assigned to a transportation network in order to estimate traffic flows and network travel conditions such as travel time. These estimated outputs from network assignment are compared against observed data such as traffic counts for model validation.

Role of Network Assignment in Travel Forecasting

The urban travel forecasting process is analyzed within the context of four decision choices:

- Personal daily activity.
- Locations to perform those activities.
- Mode of travel to activity locations, and
- Travel route to the activity locations.

A roadway transportation network in the assignment is represented by a set of links and nodes. A link represents a segment of roadway and includes physical characteristics such as estimated capacity, posted speed limit, distance, and number of lanes. A node represents the starting or ending points of a link. A node can be shared between multiple links and therefore represents connectivity between links. In public transit network, links represent a segment of a bus or railline and nodes represent stop or stations

Figure 4: Diagrammatic representation of zone boundaries, centroids, centroid connectors & links

Methods of Traffic Assignment.

There are a large number of traffic assignment methods, but they all have at their core a procedure called 'all-or-nothing' (AON) traffic assignment. All-or-nothing traffic assignment places all trips between an origin and destination on the shortest path between that origin and destination and no trips on any other possible path.

All-or-nothing Assignments

The simplest assignment algorithm is the all-or-nothing traffic assignment. In this algorithm, flows from every origin to every destination are assigned using the path finding algorithm, and travel time remains unchanged regardless of travel volumes. All-or-nothing traffic assignment

may be used when delays are unimportant for a network. Another alternative to the user-equilibrium technique is the stochastic traffic assignment technique, which assumes variation in link level travel time. One of the earliest, computationally efficient stochastic traffic assignment algorithms was developed by Robert Dial. More recently the k-shortest paths algorithm has gained popularity.

The biggest disadvantage of the all-or-nothing assignment and the stochastic assignment is that congestion cannot be considered. In uncongested networks, these algorithms are very useful. In congested conditions, however, these algorithms miss that some travellers would change routes to avoid congestion.

Figure 5: Four-step regional travel forecasting model

Other activities that were done in the planning stage include determination of the scope of works, funding of the project, provisions of drawings and layouts, and legal and environmental assessments. Proper planning further ensures flawless running of the road construction.

3.1.2. Setting out

Setting out generally refers to the process of transferring the proposed designs and drawings to the actual ground. This assists in distinguishing legal boundaries and other important structural parts of the road.

If a road is to be constructed from point A to point B, setting out is done to determine possible road alignments. The shortest link between the two points will obviously be a straight line, but the road to be constructed will hardly be entirely straight. This is because;

- a) The straight alignment may pass through immensely difficult terrain i.e. rocky or swampy areas, which might hike construction costs and/or not be passable by most vehicles.
- b) Straight alignment may lead through private properties, farms, villages and towns and it therefore doesn't make sense to destroy them to allow the road to pass through.
- c) Existence of natural body of waters such as rivers and lakes.
- d) In mountainous/hilly/rolling terrain, the gradients of a straight alignment would be really steep and therefore impassable.

In most cases, choice of alignment is influenced by:-

- a. Location of suitable soil types.
- b. Water sources.
- c. Construction costs & maintenance costs.
- d. Location of gravel deposits.
- e. Other socio-economical costs and benefits.

3.1.3. Earthworks

It is very important to carry out earthworks since this carries the road pavement. This step involves removal of topsoil (including vegetation) before grading is done, to expose the underlying ground up to the formation level. At this point, excavation stops and road construction begins.

Most earthworks are formed by cut-and-fill, and the type of fill material considered is determined in terms of its physical properties, compaction methods and conditions in which it is to be used. The soil below the formation level is known as the subgrade. Normally, this soil is tested for strength before earthworks commence to determine its quality. If the quality is low or undesirable, the soil may be removed or stabilised. If the cost of excavation of the subsoil is deemed uneconomical, sand drains and sand wicks may be used. Sand drains are typically used to

capture ground water. Sand wicks are boreholes filled with sand underneath road embankments that reduce the length that water travels in a drainage path to disintegrate water pressure. This provides great stability to the soil. Subsoil drainage is pertinent in dealing with leakage through pavements and verges from higher grounds as well as periodic rise and fall of the water table.

Strength of subgrade

During earthworks, the foremost consideration taken into place is the strength of the subgrade which determines the thickness of the road pavement. Therefore, it is important to reinforce the subgrade by;

- a) Cutting inappropriate or poor material and filling with improved material.
- b) Providing adequate subsoil drainage.
- c) Compacting subgrade to a high dry density with optimum moisture levels.
- d) Soil stabilisation procedures such as use of chemicals, cement or bituminous materials.

3.1. 4. Paving

Paving construction begins after preparation of the subgrade and, or when drainage and service ducts have been installed. A pavement in road construction is a hard surface made from strong, durable surface material that is laid down on an area that is intended to carry vehicular or foot traffic. The main function of the pavement is distribution of applied vehicular loads to the subsequent layers. This applied load should not exceed the bearing capacity of the subgrade.

A good pavement should possess the following characteristics;

- Structurally strong to be able to support the applied loads.
- Waterproof to provide an impervious surface so as to protect the subsequent layers from water damage.
- Sufficient coefficient of friction to prevent vehicles from skidding.
- Sufficient thickness to allow wheel load stresses to be safely distributed to the subgrade.
- Smooth level surface provide comfort to all road users at varying speeds.
- Dustproof to ensure traffic safety in terms of visibility.
- Noise-proof when the vehicles are traversing on it.
- Low maintenance with a long design life.

3.2. Types of pavements

The two major pavement types used in road construction are flexible pavements and rigid pavements. In flexible pavements, applied vehicular stress is transferred to the subgrade using grain-to-grain contact of the aggregates through the granular structure. Alternatively, in rigid pavements, applied vehicle loads are transferred to the subgrade soil solely through flexural strength. We also have combined pavements also known as semi-rigid pavements, which consist of a rigid pavement provided with a thin layer of flexible pavement over it. Combined pavements are the most ideal but are rarely used in new construction because of high costs.

We can simply state that flexible pavements act like flexible sheets while rigid pavements act like a rigid plate, each with its own advantages and disadvantages. Flexible pavements are more economical, can easily expand and contract simultaneously with the atmospheric temperature; but rigid pavements have a longer design life, high flexural strength and lower maintenance costs.

3.2.1. Flexible Pavements

Flexible paving, as stated earlier, involves grain-to-grain transfer of wheel loads through the points of contact in the granular layers. These wheel loads stresses act on the larger pavement area and are distributed throughout the depth of the layers, therefore necessitating the design to use the concept of a layered system. Using this concept, better quality material is used in the layers nearest to the surface to provide maximum compressive strength, while low quality material is used in the lower layers since the required strength needed to support vehicular load reduces with depth.

Types of flexible pavements include;

1. **Conventional Flexible Pavement:** Uses the layered system in which high quality materials are placed at the top of the pavement layer to resist maximum stress, and low quality materials are placed in lower layers.
2. **Full-depth Asphalt Pavements:** Bituminous layers are placed directly on the soil subgrade. Typically used when there is high traffic and local materials are unavailable.
3. **Contained Rock Asphalt Mats (CRAM):** Dense/open-graded aggregate layers are placed in between two asphalt layers. Properly designed asphalt concrete is placed above the subgrade that will reduce the vertical compressive strain on the subgrade and offer protection from surface water.

In flexible pavements, road pavement layers generally consist of the following;

Figure 6: Cross-section of flexible pavements

1. Seal coat: A thin, waterproof layer that provides skid resistance.
2. Surface course (25mm-50mm): This is the most important layer since it bears the direct traffic load and generally contains materials of good quality. Generally, the surface course is constructed with graded asphalt concrete (AC) to offer smoothness, drainage, and a hard surface to resist the distortion under traffic and provide a smooth and skid-resistant riding surface.
3. Tack coat: a little amount of asphalt emulsion diluted with water is applied to the surface to provide proper bonding. This layer must be thin, uniform and set very fast.
4. Binder course (50mm-100mm): it consists of aggregate mixed with low asphalt and doesn't require quality as high as the surface course.
5. Prime coat: applied by spreading low viscous cutback bitumen to an absorbent granular base to be able to penetrate into the below layers, plugs the voids, and form a watertight surface. It is primarily used to provide a bond between two layers
6. Base course (100mm-300mm): this is a layer of materials that provide additional load distribution, and contributes to the sub-surface drainage.
7. Sub-base course (100mm-300mm): this layer is below the base course. It provides structural support, improves drainage, and reduces intrusion of fines from the subgrade in the pavement structure.
8. Compacted subgrade (150mm-300mm): all the above pavement layers transfer stress to this layer, therefore it is essential to properly compact the layer to the desired density, near the optimum moisture content.

3.2.2. Rigid Pavements

Rigid paving involves transferring the vehicular traffic load through slab action. The road behaves like an elastic plate resting on a viscous medium and is constructed using plain cement concrete. It is placed on a well-compacted subgrade or on a single layer on granular or stabilized material.

Types of rigid pavements;

1. Jointed Plain Concrete Pavement: constructed using plain cement concrete with closely spaced contraction joints. Dowel steel bars are used for load transfer across joints. It has joint spacing of around 5m-10m.
2. Jointed Reinforced Concrete Road: constructed by placing reinforcements, which do not increase structural stability, but increase the joint spacing to around 10m-30m.
3. Continuous Reinforced Concrete Road: constructed with reinforcements but no joints.

Figure 7: Rigid pavement characteristics

4.ASPHALT PAVEMENT DISTRESSES

Kileleasha roads are typically made of Hot Mix Asphalt (HMA) pavements. As these pavements age and experience continuous traffic loading, pavement distresses begin to accumulate. Before an appropriate repair strategy can be executed, the type and extent of the deterioration must be

understood to identify the cause of the distress. Below we will look at the different types of HMA pavement distresses and their causes.

4.1. Cracking

4.1.1. Longitudinal cracking

Consists of cracks parallel to the pavement's centreline or lay down direction. These cracks allow moisture infiltration, roughness, and indicate possible onset of fatigue cracking and structural failure.

Possible causes

- Poor longitudinal joint construction.
- Reflective crack from the underlying layer.
- Pavement fatigue
- Top-down cracking.

Severity	Description	Example
Low	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Average crack width $\leq \frac{1}{4}$ inch wide or ▪ Sealed cracks with sealant in good condition and width that cannot be determined. 	
Moderate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Average crack width between $\frac{1}{4}$ and $\frac{3}{4}$ inch or ▪ Any crack with an average width $\leq \frac{3}{4}$ inches and adjacent low severity random cracking. 	
High	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Average crack width $> \frac{3}{4}$ in or ▪ Any crack with an average width $\leq \frac{3}{4}$ inches and adjacent moderate to high severity random cracking. 	

Table 2: Characteristics of longitudinal cracking

Repair

Strategies rely on the severity and extent of the cracking:

- For low severity cracks (< 1/2 inch wide and infrequent cracks), a crack seal is used to prevent entry of moisture into the subgrade through the cracks and further ravelling of the crack edges.
- For high severity cracks (> 1/2 inch wide and numerous cracks), the cracked pavement is removed and replaced with an overlay.

4.1.2. Thermal/transverse cracking

These consist of cracks perpendicular to the pavement's centreline or lay down direction. These cracks lead to moisture infiltration of the pavement layers.

Possible causes

- Shrinkage of the HMA surface due to low temperatures or asphalt binder hardening.
- Reflective crack caused by cracks beneath the surface HMA layer
- Top-down cracking.

Severity	Description	Example
Low	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Average crack width \leq 1/4 inch wide or▪ Sealed cracks with sealant in good condition and width that cannot be determined.	
Moderate	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Average crack width between 1/4 and 3/4 inch or▪ Any crack with an average width \leq 3/4 inch and adjacent low severity random cracking	
High	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Average crack width $>$ 3/4 inch or▪ Any crack with an average width \leq 3/4 inches and adjacent moderate to high severity random cracking.	

Table 3: Characteristics of thermal cracking

Repair

- For low severity cracks (< 1/2 inch wide and infrequent cracks), a crack seal is used to prevent entry of moisture into the subgrade through the cracks and further ravelling of the crack edges. HMA can provide years of satisfactory service after developing small cracks if they are kept sealed.
- For high severity cracks (> 1/2 inch wide and numerous cracks). Remove and replace the cracked pavement layer with an overlay.

4.1.3. Block cracking

These consist of interconnected cracks that seemingly divide the pavement up into rectangular pieces. Blocks range in size from approximately 1 ft² to 100 ft². Larger blocks can be generally classified as longitudinal and transverse cracking.

Possible causes

- Asphalt layer contraction and daily temperature cycling that is typically exacerbated by binder aging or binder grade or poor content selection in the mix design

Severity	Description	Example
Low	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Average crack width \leq 1/4 inch wide or▪ Sealed cracks with sealant in good condition and width that cannot be determined.	
Moderate	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Average crack width between 1/4 and 3/4 inch or▪ Any crack with an average width \leq 3/4 inches and adjacent low severity random cracking.	
High	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Average crack width $>$ 3/4 inch or▪ Cracks with an average width \leq 3/4 in and adjacent moderate to high severity random cracking.	

Table 4: Characteristics of block cracking

Repair

- For low severity cracks ($< 1/2$ inch wide), crack seal is used to prevent entry of moisture into the subgrade through the cracks and further ravelling of the crack edges. If looks are important, or cracking is extensive, a slurry seal is placed over the sealed cracks.
- For high severity cracks ($> 1/2$ inch wide and cracks with ravelled edges), the cracked pavement layer is removed and replaced with an overlay.

4.1.4. Fatigue cracking

This consists of a series of interconnected cracks caused by fatigue failure on the surface under repeated traffic loading. As the number and magnitude of loads becomes great, longitudinal cracks begin to form (usually in the wheel paths). After repeated loading, these longitudinal cracks connect forming many-sided sharp-angled pieces that develop into a pattern resembling the back of an alligator or crocodile. This leads to a myriad of problems which include roughness, structural failure, moisture infiltration into the base and subgrade, which eventually results in potholes and pavement disintegration if not treated.

Possible causes

- Decrease in pavement load-carrying capacity due to;
 - a. Loss of base or subgrade support from poor drainage. Water under a pavement generally causes the underlying materials to become weak.
 - b. Stripping of the bottom of the asphalt layer. The stripped depth contributes little to pavement strength so the effective thickness decreases.
- Increase in loading (i.e., the pavement is being loaded more heavily than anticipated in design)
- Inadequate structural design (i.e., the pavement was designed too thin for the anticipated loads)
- Poor construction (i.e., inadequate compaction)

Severity	Description	Example
Low	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ An area of cracks with no or only a few connecting cracks. ▪ Cracks are not spalled or sealed. ▪ No evidence of pumping. 	
Moderate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ An area of interconnected cracks forming a complete pattern. ▪ Cracks may be slightly spalled. ▪ Cracks may be sealed. ▪ No evidence of pumping. 	
High	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ An area of moderately or severely spalled interconnected cracks forming a complete pattern. ▪ Pieces may move when subjected to traffic. ▪ Cracks may be sealed. ▪ Pumping may be evident. 	

Table 5: Characteristics of fatigue cracking

Repair

A fatigue cracked pavement is first investigated to determine the root cause of failure. Any investigation should involve digging a pit or coring the pavement to determine the pavement's structural makeup as well as determining whether or not subsurface moisture is a contributing factor. Once the characteristic alligator pattern is apparent, repair by crack sealing is generally ineffective. Fatigue crack repair generally falls into one of two categories.

- a. Small, localized fatigue cracking indicative of a loss of subgrade support. The cracked pavement area is removed and then dug out to replace the area of poor subgrade and improve the drainage of that area. Patching is done over the repaired subgrade.
- b. Large fatigue cracked areas indicative of general structural failure. A HMA overlay is placed over the entire pavement surface that must be strong enough structurally to carry

the anticipated loading because the underlying fatigue cracked pavement most likely contributes little or no strength.

4.1.5 Slippage cracking

These are crescent or half-moon shaped cracks generally having two ends pointed into the direction of traffic. They allow moisture infiltration and make the asphalt surface rough.

Photograph 1: Example of slippage cracking in asphalt pavements

Possible causes.

- Braking or turning wheels causes the pavement surface to slide and deform. The resulting sliding and deformation is caused by;
 - a. Low-strength surface mix.
 - b. Poor bonding between the surface layer and the next underlying layer in the pavement structure.

Repair

The affected area is removed and replaced.

4.2 Surface defects

4.2.1 Ravelling

Ravelling is the process of wearing away of the pavement surface caused by the dislodging of aggregate particles and loss of asphalt binder. This ranges from loss of fines to loss of some

coarse aggregate ultimately leading to a very rough and pitted surface with obvious loss of aggregate. Loose debris on the pavement cause roughness. Also, water collecting into the ravelled locations result into vehicle hydroplaning and loss of skid resistance.

Photograph 2: Example of raveling in asphalt pavements

Possible causes

- Mechanical dislodging by certain types of vehicle tyres (studded tires, snowplough blades or tracked vehicles).
- A loss of bond between the aggregate particles and the asphalt binder as a result of:
 - Aging of the asphalt binder. Asphalt binder oxidizes as it gets older as oxygen reacts with its constituent molecules resulting in a stiffer, more viscous material that is more likely to lose aggregates on the pavement surface as they are pulled away by traffic.
 - A dust coating on the aggregate particles that forces the asphalt binder to bond with the dust rather than the aggregate.
 - Aggregate segregation. If fine particles are missing from the aggregate matrix, the asphalt binder is only able to bind the remaining coarse particles at their relatively few contact points (compared to finer particles).

- Inadequate compaction. High density is required to develop sufficient cohesion within the asphalt layer.

Repair

Ravelled pavement should be investigated to determine the root cause of failure. Repair strategies generally fall into two categories:

- a. For small, localized areas of raveling, the ravelled pavement is removed and patched. If the pavement is still structurally sound, the raveling can be fixed with a fog or slurry seal.
- b. For large ravelled areas indicative of general failure, the damaged pavement is removed and replaced with an overlay.

4.2.2 Bleeding

This consists of a film of excess asphalt binder accumulating on the pavement surface. It usually creates a shiny, glass-like reflecting surface that can become sticky when dry and slippery when wet. Bleeding may range from a surface discoloured relative to the remainder of the pavement, to a surface that is losing or has lost surface texture because of excess asphalt binder.

Photograph 3: Example of bleeding in asphalt pavements

Possible causes

Bleeding generally occurs when asphalt binder fills the remaining aggregate voids during hot weather or traffic compaction, and then expands onto the pavement surface. Since bleeding is

not reversible during cold weather or periods of low loading, asphalt binder will accumulate on the pavement surface over time. From this explanation, the most probable causes are:

- Low air void content (e.g., not enough void space for the asphalt to occupy), likely a mix design problem.
- Excessive asphalt binder either due to a poor mix design or manufacturing problems.
- Excessive application of asphalt binder during application.

Repair

- a. Minor bleeding can often be corrected by applying coarse sand to blot up the excess asphalt binder.
- b. Major bleeding can be corrected by cutting off excess asphalt with a motor grader or removing it with a heater planer. If the resulting surface is excessively rough, resurfacing may be necessary.

4.2.3. Polished aggregate

These are found in areas of the pavement where the portion of aggregate extending above the asphalt binder is either very small or there are no rough or angular aggregate particles. This usually means the surface binder has been worn away to expose coarse aggregate, therefore leading to decreased skid resistance.

Photograph 4: Example of polished aggregate

Possible causes

- Repeated traffic applications.
- Aging of the pavement. As a pavement ages, the protruding rough, angular particles become polished. This occurs quicker if the aggregate is susceptible to abrasion.

Repair

- a. Apply a skid-resistant slurry seal.
- b. Bituminous surface treatment (BST).
- c. Overlays.

4.2.4. Depression

These are localized pavement surface areas with slightly lower elevations than the surrounding pavement. They are very noticeable after rainfall, when they fill with water. Depressions filled with substantial water can cause vehicle hydroplaning.

Photograph 5: Example of depressions in asphalt pavements

Possible Causes

- Settlement of the subgrade resulting from inadequate compaction during construction.

Repair

Depressions should be repaired by removing the affected pavement then digging out and replacing the area of poor subgrade. Patching over the repaired subgrade is done.

4.3. Surface deformations.

4.3.1. Corrugation and shoving

This is a form of plastic movement typified by ripples (corrugation) or an abrupt wave (shoving) across the pavement surface, perpendicular to the traffic direction. This occurs at points where traffic starts and stops (corrugation) or areas where pavement abuts a rigid object (shoving).

Photograph 6: Example of shoving in asphalt pavements

Photograph 7: Example of corrugation in asphalt pavements

Possible Causes

This is usually caused by traffic action (starting and stopping) combined with:

- An unstable (i.e. low stiffness) HMA layer (caused by mix contamination, poor mix design, poor HMA manufacturing, or lack of aeration of liquid asphalt emulsions)
- Excessive moisture in the subgrade

Repair

A heavily corrugated or shoved pavement should be investigated to determine the root cause of failure. Repair strategies generally fall into one of two categories:

- a. For small, localized areas of corrugation or shoving, remove the distorted pavement and patch.
- b. For large corrugated or shoved areas indicative of general HMA failure, remove the damaged pavement and overlay.

4.3.2. Rutting

This involves surface depression in the wheel path whereby pavement uplift (shearing) occurs alongside the rut. Ruts are particularly evident after rainfall when they are filled with water. There are two basic types of rutting: mix rutting and subgrade rutting.

- a. Mix rutting occurs when the subgrade does not rut yet the pavement surface exhibits wheel path depressions as a result of compaction/mix design problems.
- b. Subgrade rutting occurs when the subgrade exhibits wheel path depressions due to loading.

Photograph 8: Example of rutting in asphalt pavements

Ruts filled with water can cause vehicle hydroplaning. Also, ruts can be hazardous because they tend to pull a vehicle towards the rut path as it is steered across the rut.

Possible Causes

Permanent deformation in any of a pavement's layers or subgrade is usually caused by consolidation or lateral movement of the materials due to traffic loading. Specific causes of rutting can be:

- Insufficient compaction of HMA layers during construction. HMA pavement may continue to densify under traffic loads if not compacted properly.
- Subgrade rutting (e.g., as a result of inadequate pavement structure)
- Improper mix design or manufacture (e.g., excessively high asphalt content, excessive mineral filler, insufficient amount of angular aggregate particles)

Repair

A heavily rutted pavement should be investigated to determine the root cause.

- a. Slight ruts ($< \frac{1}{3}$ inches deep) can be left untreated.
- b. Pavement with deeper ruts should be levelled and overlaid.

5. CONSTRUCTION ACTIVITIES

In this chapter, we will take a look at the construction activities undertaken in the rehabilitation of Kileleshwa roads project.

5.1 Site clearance

This is the process of clearing all bushes, vegetation, trees, rubbish and any other obstructions within the line of work. The following works were done under site clearance;

- Survey markers were established to indicate the working areas for the site clearance
- A record of existing facilities i.e. sewers, fibre cables, electricity cables was taken to ensure minimum damage was done to existing networks.
- All rubbish, marked trees, bushes, vegetation, stumps and roots were removed to their full depths.
- Vegetation on the side slopes near the road (away from the construction area) was retained to avoid the potential risk of soil erosion.
- The unusable material was removed and hauled off site

5.2. Removal of topsoil and existing AC

This involved removal of top organic soils and expansive clays up to a depth of 200mm minimum from the road construction area. Afterwards, the topsoil that is unsuitable for reuse was stockpiled and disposed by tipper trucks. The existing AC was also ripped out using a ripper that was attached to the rear end of a backhoe and pushed into the wind-rows to be reused later. Also, the existing gravel was stockpiled for reuse as fill material

Photograph 9: Removal of existing AC in Ole Kejuado road

5.3. Setting out and taking of cross-sections.

The major purpose of longitudinal and cross-section diagrams are showing the proposed levels or heights at which a road is to be constructed, as well as the existing levels of the ground. It is important that the road is constructed at the correct height or level.

The Surveyor set out the levels for the road construction using the following procedures:

1. Two reference pegs were placed at each chainage, one on each side of the road at proper right angles to the centreline and at a fixed distance of 1.5m behind the edges. All reference pegs at both horizontal and vertical curves as well as at any change of grade were hammered in.
2. A gum pole or fencing standard was placed at about 200mm behind each reference peg.
3. After all the reference pegs and poles had been placed, the level of each reference peg were be determined by the Surveyor by levelling from a benchmark with the Surveyor`s dumpy level. Forward and return levelling were done to eliminate errors in levelling.
4. Levels one metre higher than the final centreline, quarter point, and gutter levels at each particular chainage are marked on each gum pole as follows:

For cambered roads like the Kileleshwa ones;

- a. The level of the reference peg was known.
- b. The final road level at the centreline, quarter point, and gutter were read off from the cross-section.
- c. 1 metre was added to the levels obtained in **b** above.
- d. Difference in height between the top of the peg and levels obtained in **c** were obtained by subtracting **a** from **c**.
- e. The levels in **c** were then marked on the pole by placing a staff on the peg and measuring the difference calculated in **d** and making a pencil mark on the pole at the required height with the help of a set square.
- f. Alternatively, the levels in **c** were marked directly on the pole using the surveyors' level.

The levels were then transferred from the poles to the road in order set out the centreline, quarter points or gutter levels at all the chainages by adopting the following procedure:-

1. The position of the centreline, quarter points and gutters were located by measuring horizontally the required distance from one of the reference pegs in a straight line between them.

2. A line was stretched tightly from one pole to the other, holding each end on the relevant nail and then measuring down from the line a distance of 1 metre at the required point to will give the final road level at that point.
3. Surface, base, sub-base and subgrade levels were conveniently determined with the help of a wooden rod, marked up as shown below. The levels referred were always those of the tops of the layers in question.

Figure 8: Typical road structure

If the subgrade level at the centreline was required to be set out on a cambered road, the string was stretched between points A1 on opposite poles and the gauge rod held at the centreline with the subgrade mark against the string. The bottom of the rod will then be at the proposed subgrade level.

If the subgrade level at the gutter line was required, the string was stretched between points C1 on the poles and the gauge rod held at the gutter line position with the sub-grade mark against the string. The bottom of the rod again denoted the subgrade level at that point.

Figure 9: Setting out levels for different road layers

The subgrade level at the quarter point can similarly be found by stretching the string between point B1 and holding the gauge with the subgrade mark against the string.

5.4. Cut to spoil/fill for vertical alignment

This process involved setting out of batters for cuts and fills. Batters pegs were normally set at 20 metres distance normal to the centreline. The process generally required:-

- Poles to be painted white and distances written on front and back of poles sufficiently large to be discernible at a distance.
- When batter boards were erected, it was unnecessary to use red paint to indicate cuts.
- Use of company standard colours, and when fills were not excessive, auxiliary poles were erected showing formation levels.
- Slope distances taken for cross-sections
- Each cross-section was carefully considered, and a sketch made and taken into the field to aid in setting out.
- In fairly shallow cuts, levels were to be given on plies on the centreline.
- Poles to remain until required depth was obtained, and then cut out.
- Fills to be re-centred and new batters placed at each 2 metre.
- Coloured insulating tape for standard slopes.
- Centre- line poles on high fills were to be extended vertically as the layers were added to maintain the centreline.
- When cut or fill reached sub-grade level (approximately), pegs were to be placed to ensure that the cut (or fill) was wide enough

5.5. Processing of the sub-base layer

Since the project mostly involves rehabilitation of the road, the existing road was ripped up to the previous base layer which was 300mm deep. Improved murrum mixed with the previous AC that was stockpiled was spread out and thoroughly processed using a grader. Extra measures were taken to ensure that this layer did not contain more than 30% of bituminous material by volume and larger than 37.5mm by size. After being processed, the sub-base was compacted by a single drum roller to a thickness of 150mm to form a hard, impervious surface.

Photograph 10: Grader processing the subbase layer in Vihiga Road

Photograph 11: Vibrating roller compacting the subbase layer in Vihiga Road

5.6. Hand packing of the base layer

Hand packed stone base consisted of a layer of hand laid stone of defined size and durable in nature, that is laid in a manner such that when proof-rolled and compacted, it forms a stable and dense matrix as a road base.

Photograph 12: Hand packed base layer in Kandara Road

a) Materials for Hand Packed Stone Base

This consisted of durable stone with nominal base dimensions of 75 mm square and a minimum height of 180 mm or when compacted, to give a layer of 150 mm. The stone shall be class C with the following requirements:

Los Angeles Abrasion test (LAA)	45 max
Aggregate Crushing value test (ACV)	32 max
Soundness test (SSS)	12 max
Flakiness Index test (FI)	30 max
Core Recovery (CR)	60 min.

Material had to be free from foreign matter.

b) Laying of Hand Packed Stone Base

Photograph 13: Laying of hand packed stone base in Vihiga Road

The stone was laid by hand closely together, and then wedged into place by ramming smaller stone chips into the joints using hammers and steel rods. The base of the stone alternated with the apex in all directions. Afterwards, the layer was proof rolled using a loaded truck with minimum axle load of 8 tonnes to be approved of its stability before compaction.

c) Compaction

This was done by a steel wheeled roller of 14 tonnes which did four static runs or until no movement was detected under the roller. Following that, vibratory compaction was done until an average dry density of 85% minimum of specific gravity of stone had been achieved. The surface of the compacted layer was levelled using quarry dust (0/6mm), with the following specifications:

The stone was class C.

Grading

Sieve Size	%Passing
10	100
6.3	90-100
4	75-95
2	50-70

1	33-50
0.425	20-33
0.300	16-28
0.150	10-20
0.075	6-12

The dust was free from foreign matter. Maximum allowable layer was 40 mm.

5.7. Installation of road kerbs and channels for edge restraints on the carriageway

Road kerbs serve the following purposes;

- They retain the carriageway edge to prevent spreading of material and loss of structural integrity.
- Act as a barrier or demarcation between road traffic and pedestrian walkways or verges.
- Provides a sort of physical check to prevent vehicles leaving the carriageway
- Forms a channel along which surface water can be drained

The most commonly used are Pre-Cast Concrete (P.C.C) road kerbs, especially the half-battered profile ones.

Figure 10: Characteristics of half-battered kerbs

These kerbs provide an element sufficient enough to warn motorists that they are dangerously close to the edge of the carriageway, while the sloping back profile enables road rollers to operate right up to the edge of the pavement without scratching or damaging the kerb face when the surfacing is laid. They are normally used where a footpath is provided adjacent to the carriageway. Channels on the other hand, are placed on the inner edge of the road kerbs, right next to the end of the carriageways.

Laying of the kerbs

This process was split into 3 simple operations;

- a) Preparation and laying out of the bedding

The bedding consisting C15 concrete was laid out at an approximate thickness of 150mm before compaction, along where the channels and kerbs were required. This is sometimes known as windrow bedding. The blinding was done 10 or so linear metres at a time and compacted to 100mm by trampling, and then smoothed with a trowel or a spade. Extra bedding was added if required.

Photograph 14: Blinding for kerbs in Ole Kejuado Road

Preparation is done using the below table which shows coverage rates for the most popular types of channels and kerbs.

Unit (H x W x L) All on 100mm bed	Bed Width: (mm)	Haunch Width: (mm)	Haunch Height: (mm)	Bedding per m ³ (lin m)	Haunching per m ³ (lin m)	Bed + Haunch per m ³ (lin m)
Edging Kerb: 150x50x915mm	150 ~ 250	100 ~ 150	125	38 ~ 63	51 ~ 76	22 ~ 28
Edging Kerb: 200x50x915mm	150 ~ 250	100 ~ 150	175	38 ~ 63	36 ~ 54	19 ~ 23
Road Kerb: 150x125x915mm	250 ~ 300	100 ~ 150	100	32 ~ 38	63 ~ 95	21 ~ 24
Road Kerb: 250x125x915mm	250 ~ 300	100 ~ 150	200	32 ~ 38	32 ~ 48	16 ~ 17
Road Kerb: 300x150x915mm	275 ~ 325	100 ~ 150	250	29 ~ 35	25 ~ 38	14 ~ 15
Block Kerb: 125x125x100mm	250 ~ 300	75 ~ 125	100	32 ~ 38	76 ~ 127	22 ~ 25
Block Kerb: 200x125x100mm	250 ~ 300	75 ~ 125	100	32 ~ 38	76 ~ 127	22 ~ 25
Brick edging: 50x100x200mm	225 ~ 275	75 ~ 125	35	35 ~ 42	217 ~ 362	30 ~ 35
Brick edging: 50x200x100mm	325 ~ 375	75 ~ 125	35	25 ~ 29	217 ~ 362	23 ~ 26

Allows for 5% wastage

Table 6: Coverage rates for kerbs and channels

b) Laying the road kerbs and channels

Photograph 15: Laying of kerbs and channels in Ole Kejuado Road

The channels and kerbs were placed on top of the C15 concrete bedding, and tapped down to the required level using a small rubber mallet. A piece of timber was held on top of the channels,

so that there's less danger of spalling the surface. A string line guide was followed closely and the seated kerb/channels were ensured to never be more than 30mm above or below the line.

It was important to be as accurate as possible to ensure levels and gradients were as planned, and the top face of the channels/kerb were checked for levels across not along the units. A spirit level was used to check levels back to the string line guide.

c) Haunching of the road kerbs and channels

Photograph 16: Haunching of kerbs and channels in Kandara Road

The haunching concrete was placed at the back (i.e. outside edge) of the channels. As a rule of thumb, the haunching concrete was made to be at least the width of the channels/kerbs it was supporting, or 75mm minimum for residential footpaths, 100mm minimum for driveways, and 100-150mm wide for major roads. The haunching concrete was then compacted and

smoothened with the back of a trowel or spade. The tighter this concrete is compacted, the stronger it will be when it finally sets.

Laying to curves and arcs

Figure 11: Basic geometry for arcs and circles

An arc comprises a number of important features shown in the drawing above. The **origin** is the centre of the arc. The **radius** of the arc is measured between the origin and the face of the kerb unit. The **tangent points** are the start and end points of the arc, the points where they join a straight line or another arc. A **chord** is a straight line between any two points on the arc. The size of the arc will determine the best way of setting-out, particularly establishing any intermediate points that may be used as guides during the laying of the arc. For example, consider the 600mm arc shown here on a layout for 100mm block paving kerb units.

Figure 12: Laying 100mm block paving kerbs to an arc

The purple line, representing the working line/level guide, is stretched from Tangent Point B to Tangent Point C. However, by establishing an intermediate point, marked on the diagram as E, accurate laying of the kerb line becomes much easier.

On larger arcs, with larger kerb/channels units, the distance between these intermediate points can be extended, but, ideally it should never exceed approximately 4 metres.

Figure 13: Laying kerbs to longer arcs

On the 4.5m radius of road kerbs illustrated above, intermediates have been established at points C and D, reducing the distance between reference points to around 2.5m and bringing the level guide considerably closer to the work than would be the case with a line strung from the two Tangent Points at A and B.

Many curves and arcs can be laid using standard kerbs and channels. However, there comes a point when the individual units are skewed to such an extent that an unacceptably wide joint is presented between adjacent units. Just when this wide joint occurs depends on the size of the radius and the size of the units being used as kerbs or channels.

5.8. Surfacing with Asphalt Concrete on the carriageway.

Asphalt Concrete (AC) is basically comprised of aggregate bound together into a solid mass by an asphalt binder (also known as asphalt cement or liquid asphalt). Approximately 93-96% of the mixture by weight consists of aggregates and the approximately 4%-7% is asphalt binder.

Asphalt is manufactured in a central mixing plant where the binder and aggregates are heated, properly proportioned, and mixed. Other renditions of asphalt include hot mix asphalt (HMA), warm mix asphalt (WMA), plant mix asphalt, asphalt concrete, bituminous concrete, blacktop, or Superpave.

Benefits of asphalt

- **It is durable.** Because of their flexible nature, asphalt pavements are long-lasting and withstand overloading without much damage.
- **It is versatile.** HMA pavements are designed to handle all kinds of traffic loading, can be used to salvage old road pavements as well as building new ones.
- **It is economical.** Asphalt mixes are usually ready-to-use, can be constructed rapidly, and require minimal maintenance; all while providing outstanding performance.

- **It is sustainable.** Asphalt pavements can 100% be recycled to make Reclaimed Asphalt Pavement (RAP), Recycled Asphalt Shingles (RAS) etc.
- **It provides adequate safety.** Asphalt pavements offer high skid resistance, have reduced glare and provide contrast with white or yellow road markings.
- **It is smooth.** Asphalt pavements are smooth and uniform and can improve fuel efficiency.

Asphalt Pavement Design Considerations in Kileleshwa Roads

When it comes to designing asphalt pavements, we consider three elements namely: **Traffic**, **subgrade** and **drainage**.

1. **Traffic**

Pavements are designed to carry different types of vehicles in the traffic stream including automobiles, light trucks, buses, heavy commercial trucks (trailers), and construction equipment, among other vehicle types and loads. In Kileleshwa, the main component of most traffic streams are passenger vehicles, but the primary consideration in pavement design is heavy trucks. This is because heavy trucks impart far more vehicular stress on pavements compared to automobiles and thus are the primary contributors to pavement damage. Based on the axle load distribution factors (Kenya Road Design Manual, 1987), a loaded 5-axle trailer imparts more than 1600 times more damage than a typical passenger car and more than 200 times greater than a large sport utility vehicle (SUV). Below are the various types of traffic classes outlined in the Kenyan Road Design manual:-

- Traffic Class 1 (T1):** This class has the heaviest traffic volume class that accommodates 2500-6000 standard axles per day, and also carry a huge number of heavy commercial vehicles.
- Traffic Class 2 (T2):** This is a medium duty traffic class which still has a relatively high volume of standard axles at 1000-2000 per day.
- Traffic Class 3 (T3):** This class consists majorly of transit routes which include buses, and consists of 300-100 standard axles per day.
- Traffic Class 4 (T4):** This class sees some, but not much regular traffic and includes mostly cars on residential streets which accumulate to around 100-300 standard axles per day.

E) Traffic Class 5 (T5): This is the lightest duty pavement and doesn't consist regular traffic. Most traffic is passenger car traffic which accumulates to around 25-100 standard axles per day.

Most of the roads in this project consist of traffic classes T3-T5.

2. Subgrade.

In the case of a pavement structure, its success highly depends on the quality of the subgrade that the pavement is constructed upon. A higher quality (or stronger) subgrade can withstand greater stresses, which means that the thickness of the pavement structure can be reduced compared to that needed for a weaker subgrade. For this reason, it is important that the subgrade soil be thoroughly examined and understood before developing a pavement design. It has been proven that there is good relation between the California Bearing Ratio and the elastic modulus of Kenyan soils. Therefore, CBR testing is used as means of evaluating the subgrade bearing strength.

A survey done on Kenyan subgrade soils indicated the following 6 bearing strength classes:-

Soil Class	CBR Range	Median	Comments
S1	2-5	3.5	These soils are poor quality and should not be used as direct support for the pavements. They should be excavated and replaced with improved subgrade.
S2	5-10	7.5	These soils can be used as direct support for the pavement as they are of good quality.
S3	7-13	10	
S4	10-18	14	
S5	15-30	22.5	These consist of gravelly material or unsoaked material.
S6	30		In the case of these materials, no sub-base is required.

Table 7: Bearing strength classes of Kenyan soils

For CBRs below 2, it's out of the question to lay a pavement on these soils because they have poor bearing capacities. We can also classify subgrade to **good, medium** and **poor**.

	Poor	Medium	Good
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Becomes soft and plastic when wet. ✓ Clays and fine silts <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ≥50% passing No. 200 ✓ Coarse silts and sandy loams <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deep frost penetration • High water table 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Retains a moderate degree of firmness under adverse moisture conditions. ✓ Loams, silty sands, and sandy-gravels containing moderate amounts of fine silts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Retains a substantial amount of load-supporting capacity when wet. ✓ Clean sands, sand-gravels, and those free of detrimental amounts of plastic fines. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ≤10% passing No. 200 ✓ Relatively unaffected by moisture or frost.
Typical Properties	CBR < 6 LL > 40 PI > 10 GI > 4	CBR: 6–9 LL: 25–40 PI: 6–10 GI: 2–4	CBR ≥ 10 LL < 25 PI < 6 GI < 2

Table 8: Subgrade categories

3. Drainage

For your asphalt pavement to be long lasting, you need to provide proper drainage to divert water away from the pavement structure. Soils become weaker with increase in moisture content. This then causes expansive soils to increase in volume which could result to heaving in the pavement structure. There are two types of drainage for pavement: Surface and subsurface drainage.

Surface drainage

Surface drainage involves the removal of water present on the surface of the pavement, shoulder, and adjacent ground. For good surface drainage, the pavement and shoulders must be sloped properly to ensure the flow of water off the roadway to kerbs and gutters or to adjacent drainage ditches or swales. It is recommended to use a cross-slope of at least 2% for roads with two or more lanes. Cross-slopes of less than 1% are not practical because there's a possibility of flat spots or depressions forming, that could result in areas where water may puddle (bird baths) and not be removed from the pavement surface. If bird baths are present on a pavement surface, then there is a possibility that the water will seep into the pavement structure through cracks in the surface of the pavement depending on the condition. With adequate flow of water across the pavement surface, it is important to ensure that surface runoff is collected and channelled off the pavement to a properly designed stormwater collection system. This will minimize the chance of water seeping into the pavement structure or subgrade.

When a pavement is not surrounded by kerbs, drainage ditches should be constructed adjacent to the pavement to collect and divert water away from the pavement. As seen below, water flows from the pavement and shoulder surfaces down the pavement foreslope into a rounded ditch

area. A back slope leads from the bottom of the ditch up to intercept runoff from the adjacent land. The adjacent land is frequently sloped toward the ditch and can contribute to a significant portion of the flow in the drainage ditch.

Figure 14: Surface drainage off of a pavement surface into a roadside drainage ditch or kerbs and gutter

Subsurface drainage

Subsurface drainage involves removal of water contained in, or moving through the various layers of the pavement structure or the adjacent soil. Relatively high moisture content substantially reduce the load carrying capacity of the soil and base material and some soils can undergo volumetric changes as the moisture content fluctuates. Additionally, water accumulation within asphalt layers can cause stripping of the asphalt binder from the aggregate, which deteriorates the pavement.

If the pavement surface becomes cracked, water penetrates into the pavement surface and infiltrates the pavement structure and subgrade. Water can also rise from the subgrade beneath the pavement structure due to changes in water table elevations and water draining into the subgrade from adjacent areas. In situations when water accumulates within the pavement structure, it is necessary to include under drains, interceptor drains, edge drains, and/or drainage layers with the purpose of diverting water from the pavement structure and preventing water accumulation.

AC surface course construction

1. Application of prime coat.

Photograph 17: Application of prime coat in Kandara Road

MC-30 was the medium curing cutback bitumen used as prime coat in this project. It contains 42% kerosene and 58% penetration grade 80/100. Application of MC-30 as prime coat was done to the granular base layer in preparation for the AC surfacing in order to:-

- a. Coat and bond loose materials/particles onto the base layer surface of the road.
- b. Harden/toughen the base surface to be able to provide a working platform for the construction equipment.
- c. Plug the capillary voids in the base layer to prevent the migration of moisture.
- d. Provide sufficient adhesion between the base and surface courses.
- e. Waterproof the base course.

Procedure

Step 1: Before priming, the weather was confirmed to be conducive (sunny/slightly cloudy) for priming to begin.

Step 2: All the loose dirt and other disapproved materials were swept away, first, by hand brooms, then by using a dust blower.

Step 3: Once the carriageway was confirmed to be fully dry, the MC-30 cutback bitumen was applied uniformly to the base layer surface using a pressure distributor truck. This was to be done one side (LHS/RHS) at a time. In areas where the carriageway was wider, the truck made one pass along the centreline of the road.

Step 4: The rates of spraying were measured at 60-meter intervals, on both the left and right sides of the road, with 0.09m² trays. This was done by recording the weight of the tray and the weight of the tray+MC-30 bitumen. The weight of the bitumen was got by subtraction and spray rate got by dividing weight of bitumen by the area of the tray. The average spray rate of the distributor was approximately 0.86-1.0 L/m².

Step 5: Hand spraying was then done using the hand nozzles of the pressure distributor to fix small patches that were not primed adequately.

2. Application of tack coat.

K1-60 cationic bitumen was applied as tack coat, prior to paving. It consists of medium-viscosity, emulsified asphalt containing a minimum of 57% bitumen. This product conforms to BS434: Part 2 whereby the prefix 'K' means cationic emulsion, '1' means rapid breaking emulsion and the number after the hyphen '60' is the bitumen content. Tack coating is necessary in order to provide a bond between two asphalt layers to minimize the risk of spillage between the base and surface courses, and ensure that pushing and sliding of A.C material is reduced to allow for proper compaction.

Procedure

Step 1: Before application, the tack coat metallic drums were well rolled to agitate the K1-60 emulsion.

Step 2: The drums were then mounted onto the hand spraying machine.

Step 3: Spraying was done evenly and in one direction. When the emulsion was initially sprayed onto the paving surface, it had a brown colour. After the tack coat broke, it turned black in colour and became sticky indicating that it was ready for the next AC layer.

Photograph 18: Application of tack coat in Kandara Road

3. Laying the AC layer.

As stated before, AC consists of aggregate, sand and asphalt cement mixture that is used as the final, surface course of a road pavement. Hot mix asphalt (HMA) was used in this project.

Procedure

Step 1: AC was delivered to the site by tipper trucks which subsequently parked in front of the paving machine at the chainage 0+000 of the road.

Step 2: The site surveyor marked the road centreline so that the paving machine could adequately be adjusted to lay the AC with a camber.

Step 3: The temperature of the AC in the tipper trucks was measured and found to be no less than 100 °C.

Step 4: The tipper truck deposited the AC onto the conveyor belt of the paving machine, which then processed it and laid it with its mechanical spreader. The asphalt concrete surface layer was placed in one layer.

Step 5: Dipsticks were inserted randomly throughout the laying process to ensure that the AC was laid to an uncompacted thickness of 70mm.

Step 6: Temperature was checked before compaction and found to be around 90-100°C.

Step 7: The layer was then compacted to a compacted thickness of 50mm, ensuring the finished grade was controlled by the site surveyor. Rolling and compaction started as soon as the asphalt material was laid without displacement and this continued until it was thoroughly compacted and all roller marks removed. Proper compaction of the surface course ensures a strong, smooth, and watertight pavement wearing course.

Step 8: Temperature was checked again after compaction to ensure compacted temperature did not fall by more than 5°C from the un-compacted temperature.

5.9. Overlays

An overlay is generally a layer of asphalt that is placed on top of an existing asphalt pavement structure that requires preventative maintenance or rehabilitation. There are two types of overlays;

1. Preservation overlays.
2. Structural overlays.

Preservation overlay.

These overlays are designed to preserve the condition of a pavement that is already in good condition (has low severity cracking and rutting). This type of overlay is typically thin ($\frac{1}{2}$ – 1 inch) and is sometimes referred to as a **thinlay**. Thin asphalt overlays are usually effective because of their ability to;

- a. Provide a new smooth surface that improves the ride quality in terms of comfortability.
- b. Reduce the noise levels from low tire pavement noise generation.
- c. Maintain the original surface geometrics by maintaining camber and/or crossfall grade, and slope with minimal effect on the road drainage, especially with small nominal maximum aggregate size mixtures.
- d. Reduce life cycle maintenance costs through increased pavement service life when placed on pavements that are structurally strong
- e. Reduce the pavement distress from heavy traffic loading and high shear stresses acting on the pavement.
- f. Provide long-lasting service that is easily maintained with no asphalt binder runoff or loose aggregate.

It is generally recommended to use this type of overlay on pavements with low to medium levels of surface distress and it should be placed before pavement deterioration becomes critical. If designed properly, the thin overlays provide 10 or more years of performance before rehabilitation is needed.

Structural overlays

These overlays are used to restore the structural capacity of given asphalt pavement. In general, the overlay thickness depends on the difference between the required structural capacity needed and the structural integrity of the existing pavement structure.

Construction of overlays

Photograph 19: Overlay construction

Step 1: Patching of the existing pavement was done. If milling had been planned, full depth patching was to be done prior to milling to improve the overall smoothness of the finished pavement.

Step 2: Milling of the existing surface was done to:

- a. Remove defects that could reflect through to the surface
- b. Roughen the surface in order to strengthen the bond between overlay and the surface with proper tack application, thereafter providing a greater degree of skid resistance.

NB: The reclaimed asphalt pavement (RAP) from milling can be processed and recycled into new asphalt mixtures. Once the milling was complete, the old pavement surface was swept clear of all debris before any tack coat was applied.

Step 3: Milling around the sidewalks or edge restraints was done to help maintain the kerb height clearance and the drainage.

Step 4: Levelling was done to fill depressions before the overlay was fully laid. Fine aggregate size was recommended to allow for very thin lifts in order to fairly transition to the existing pavement grade.

Step 5: Paving was done after proper surface preparation and the application of the tack coat. The tack coat helps bond the new overlay to the old pavement.

During this process, screed control is critical to ensure the proper mat thickness on thinlays and also to ensure the old and new pavement are in close proximity so that there's shear forces created by vehicles during braking and turning movements. It is also of importance to remove existing pavement markings (thermoplastic markings) prior to placement.

Step 6: Compaction was done so as to increase the stability of the mat and to seal the voids in the material in order to make it as impermeable as possible. Mat density was best achieved in thin lifts using a static, steel-wheel compactor.

Vibratory rollers should not be used on thin lifts that are less than about one inch because they may cause roughness or tearing of the mat.

5.10. Installation of culverts and Invert Block Drains (IBDs).

Construction of pipe culverts

Photograph 20: Construction of pipe culvert in Vihiga Road

1. Trench excavation was done for the pipe culvert.

The trench excavation was done to the proper lines and levels as ascertained by the surveyor to provide for the whole structure's dimensions under the road pavement layers.

The table below shows the proposed trench width for all pipe diameters in consideration. The extra width of excavation provides space for the surround.

TRENCH WIDTH FOR CONCRETE PIPE			
Pipe Diameter (inches)	Trench Width (feet)	Pipe Diameter (millimeters)	Trench Width (millimeters)
4	1.6	100	470
6	1.8	150	540
8	2.0	200	600
10	2.3	250	680
12	2.5	300	800
15	3.0	375	910
18	3.4	450	1020
21	3.8	525	1100
24	4.1	600	1200
27	4.5	675	1300
33	5.2	825	1600
36	5.6	900	1700
42	6.3	1050	1900
48	7.0	1200	2100
54	7.8	1350	2300
60	8.5	1500	2500
66	9.2	1650	2800
72	10.0	1800	3000
78	10.7	1950	3200
80	11.4	2100	3400
90	12.1	2250	3600
96	12.9	2400	3900
102	13.6	2550	4100
108	14.3	2700	4300
114	14.9	2850	4500
120	15.6	3000	4800
126	16.4	3150	5000
132	17.1	3300	5200
138	17.8	3450	5400
144	18.5	3600	5600

Table 9: Trench widths for concrete pipe culverts

2. Bedding for the pipe culvert.

This was done to provide a firm foundation of uniform density throughout the full length of the culvert. The surveyor first checked the specific levels for the bed before C15 concrete of 100-150mm thickness was laid. This bed was well cured before construction proceeded.

3. Laying the pipes.

Proper care was taken when unloading and lowering the concrete pipes to ensure safety of the workers, and also to prevent structural strain or damage to the culvert from falls and impact. The pipes were laid from the outlet towards the inlet, at the specified lines and grade. During the laying procedure, the pipes were fitted and matched into each other in order to ensure a smooth uniform invert.

4. Jointing of the pipes.

This was done to ensure adjacent pipe inner and outer diameter edges flushed.

5. Surround for the pipes

Formwork was placed around the whole structure and C15 concrete was used for the pipe surround. A vibrating poker was used to remove air voids so as to provide more compressive strength.

6. Curing.

The structure surround was cured with water, 3 times a day for 3 days.

Construction of Invert Block Drains (IBDs)

1. Extraneous material was stripped and removed. This included vegetation and roots in the drain trenches.
2. The existing masonry drains were demolished.
3. The surveyor set out and marked the alignment for the trench to be properly dug out.
4. Preparations for the bed were undertaken by:-
 - a. Ensuring the bed and invert levels were adequate for proper free flow of water.
 - b. Ensuring the bed material was dry and free from organic matter and expansive clays.
5. The bed was then properly levelled and compacted using a plate compactor.
6. The site surveyor ensured the compacted level was adequate and thereafter set out for the IBD alignment and invert levels.

Photograph 21: Construction of Invert Block Drains in Mandera Road

7. The IBDs were then laid simultaneously to ensure the IBD inverts and access/cross culverts inverts flushed.
8. Side slabs were then laid on both sides of the drain ensuring the joints were interchangeable. This was done in 1, 2 or 3 layers.

NB: Side slabs are used to prevent any soil or material from entering the drain. This prevents siltation or blockage in the drain.

9. Jointing was then done on the whole structure using a mortar mix (1cement:3sand). Approximately 10-15mm thick joints were done
10. Proper curing was done using water, 3 times a day for 3 days.

6. CONCLUSION

6.1. Challenges and recommendations

S/No.	Challenges	Recommendation
1	Non-adherence by site workers to Health and Safety matters. Most workers did not have safety boots or helmets. (They had reflectors which is a positive recommendation)	Contractor to provide protective gear to all the workers in site.
2	Performance challenges during construction for drainage structures such as IBDs and access/cross culverts.	A thorough and detailed stormwater and sewer management master plan.
3	Guidance on execution of footpath scope as whole.	KURA Engineer to address this.
4	Non-cooperation of Kileleshwa residents during construction of the road structures. Some residents removed prime coats during construction of some roads using vehicles. Some residents were also speeding adjacent to road construction workers on site posing a big risk to their safety	Proper policies and notices to be administered to the residents. Proper civil education to be taught about the importance of respecting road construction procedures.

Table 10: Challenges and recommendations

6.2. Safety, health and environment

There were no accidents or incidents reported on site in the month of February, March and April 2022. The Contractor tried to adhere to the safety regulations by provide Personal Protective Equipment to his personnel. The Contractor also erected warning signs and barrier tapes around ongoing works and proper route diversion signage.

APPENDICES

Photograph 22: Reclaimed Asphalt Material (RAM) in Ole Kejuado Road

Photograph 23: Removal of wet soil material on the IBD bed

Photograph 24: Completed cross culvert in Vihiga Road

Photograph 25: Completed Asphalt Concrete pavement on Kandara Road

Photograph 26: Excavation of Trench for cross culvert in Vihiga Road

Photograph 27: Jointing of the pipe culvert in Nyeri Road

Photograph 28: Road Signage used for diversion of vehicles during laying of AC

Photograph 29: Rock fill used to improve Subbase layer in Vihiga Road

Photograph 30: Sand used to aid fast curing of cross culvert in Kandara Road

Photograph 31: Simultaneous paving and compaction of AC layer in Kandara Road

Photograph 32: Construction of access culvert in Vihiga Road

Photograph 33: Construction of Invert Block Drains in Mandera Road

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